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Summary sheet

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About ReVeAL

ReVeAL - Regulating Vehicle Access for Improved Liveability - is a CIVITAS project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The goal of ReVeAL is to add Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVAR) to the standard range of urban mobility transition approaches of cities across Europe. The EU funded R&I ReVeAL project looks at this hot topic for the first time since the CURACAO project (ending a decade ago).

The overarching mission of the project is to enable cities to optimise urban space and transport network usage, through new and integrated packages of urban vehicle access policies and technologies. Such policies can lead to fewer emissions, less noise as well as improved accessibility and quality of life, which especially benefits the people living in these cities. These policies bring the possibility of encouraging more sustainable transport choices, enabling cities to become more liveable, ultimately healthier and more attractive for every member of society.

To this end, ReVeAL combines conceptual work and case study research with hands-on UVAR implementation in six pilot cities, as well as systematic stakeholder interaction through professional communication activities. Different UVAR measures will be developed, implemented and tested in the cities of: Helmond (NL), Jerusalem (IL), London (UK), Padova (IT), Vitoria-Gasteiz (ES) and the project leader Bielefeld (DE). Beyond these cities, the project partners of ReVeAL are Centro de Estudios Ambientales (ES), Ghent University (BE), Università di Padova (IT), POLIS (BE), Rupprecht Consult (DE), Sadler Consultants (DE), Transport for London (UK), TRT (IT), V-Tron (NL) and WSP Sweden (SE). The project started in June 2019 and will run for three years.

ReVeAL looks at a range of UVAR measures, both established and cutting-edge approaches, grouped under the four *Measure Fields*:

Zero-emission zones

Areas where only vehicles emitting zero emissions are permitted.

Spatial interventions

Access regulations based on area planning and design, and physical interventions in the public realm.

Pricing measures

Financial charging for accessing specific areas.

Future proofing and future options

Possible tools and emerging technologies that cut across all measures.

Description of deliverable

This report is based on findings from a literature overview as well as an international workshop session held online on October 15, 2020. In this report implementation barriers to dynamic curbside management are described and an initial introduction to the topic is given. This report builds on the findings of the report *Market Consultation on new technology, products and policy measures* (milestone 10). The identified barriers and solutions will guide the development of a 'sandbox' plan that will be carried out within the Eastern Cluster area in the City of London.

The introduction to curbside management will be further developed into a final report (deliverable 3.9) due in month 36 including a description of the set-up and the findings from the actual test in London.

Methodology

The purpose of this report is to:

1. Explore and define the topic
2. Understand present and future needs of different types of curbside demands
3. Identify and understand barriers for future implementation
4. Systematically describe barriers as well as ways to overcome them.

The report is a synthesis of findings from both a literature overview and an international workshop held on October 15, 2020 with representatives from 'leading cities'¹, external experts and members of the ReVeAL consortium.

The literature overview was carried out (1) to gain an understanding of the topic, (2) to map common research questions and relevant case studies and their findings, and (3) to summarise existing material relating to the topic. The starting point for the literature search was the recommendations in the ITF's report (2018) on curbside management from where a selection of initial keywords was identified. The search was step-by-step narrowed down to the most relevant keywords or combinations thereof and limited in time to sources published after 2010. The literature search resulted in around 150 documents which then were sorted with descriptive tags. The initial outcome of the literature overview was presented at the workshop held on October 15, 2020.

To structure our findings regarding barriers and possible solutions we're using the framework of the four ReVeAL Transition Area. This framework has been developed to support the understanding of how change processes and new measures are managed in cities. The Transition Areas are as follows:

- **Governance and financing** (legal, political, procedural issues and UVAR financing mechanisms)
- **User needs and public acceptance** (demands and needs, acceptance of regulation, willingness to pay, value of time, etc.)
- **System design and UVAR technologies** (data-driven planning, smart enforcement systems, connected traveler etc.)
- **Mobility concepts** (accompanying mobility services and measures).

¹ 'Leading cities' are cities which are understood as having worked with the topic and who have already addressed the growing demands for curbside access for a longer period time.

Introduction to Dynamic Curbside Management

The starting point for much of the interest in curbside² management is the growing competition for curb access, fuelled by the rise of goods deliveries and ride services. This is evident in recent reports with recommendations for better curb management, among others the International Transport Forum (ITF) report “The Shared-Use City: Managing the Curb” (2018) and the Institute of Transportation Engineers (ITE) report “Curbside management practitioners guide” (2018). Both reports are in-part written with the perspectives from private companies such as car manufacturers, technology providers and mobility service providers. The ITE report for example highlights a case study prepared for Uber (2018), performed by the same consultant that wrote the report.

Both the ITF and the ITE reports however build on the report “Curb Appeal: Curbside Management Strategies for Improving Transit Reliability” (2017) written by the American National Association of City Transportation Officials (NACTO). Even though the NACTO report, as the title reveals, focuses on curbside management from a transit perspective, it also includes tools and measures for other functions and needs. The main common theme in all reports is the shift from storage for vehicles to other functions.

The growing pressure from mainly freight deliveries and ride services is a driving force behind most of the works that have been done regarding curbside management in the academic field and the focus of most on-street trials. This development is also the focus for our task within the ReVeAL project.

Defining Dynamic Curbside Management

This report proposes dynamic curbside management to be defined as

“...the management of curb adjacent space according to the time-varying need and demand of different uses or users.”

A definition is needed first and foremost to establish a common understanding of the topic within the ReVeAL project and will also be included in the work-in-progress *ReVeAL Glossary*. A definition has the opportunity to make the topic more accessible for a wide public, especially when moving into the field of standardisation.

Functions and uses

Some descriptions of curbside management also include the moving traffic lane adjacent to the curb, the possibility to alter the street section and moving the curb, and/or what happens on both sides of the curb. See for example the strategies in the “Seattle Right-of-Way Improvements Manual” (2019) or the

² For this document the words curb and curbside are used, when describing the curb-adjesant space, instead of curb and curbside.

San Francisco MTA “Curb Management Strategy” (2020). The proposed definition is wide enough to include all the descriptions above.

However, to be able to better understand the topic, there is a need to further delimit and define what curbside management is about. Even though cities tend to include moving traffic or mobility as a function when discussing or outlining strategies for the allocation of curb space, curbside management is recognized to be about what needs to ‘happen’ at the curb and not in the whole width of a street.

One example is the introduction of a bus lane. The placing of a bus lane corresponds with the traffic volume in the street, or in the transport corridor. Further, a bus lane doesn’t necessarily need to be placed next to the curb. The decision to introduce a bus lane next to the curb in a street of course very much affects and limits other uses of the curb. It’s however a decision that is taken within a systemwide transportation and mobility framework and not within a curbside management framework, although the curbside management approach can provide important input. The need for bus stops however is a stationary function that belongs to the curbside management framework.

Except from moving traffic, curbside management is also affected by, and sometimes overlapping, other areas such as the management of carparking, freight, stormwater, green space, etc. Tools and functions that are in-use or placed somewhere else can often have a great effect on the demands and needs at the curb. The provision of off-street parking is one of many examples in this regard. Measures which are implemented somewhere else are here viewed as complementary measures and not part of the curbside management framework presented below.

Curbside management framework

Our proposed framework sees local mobility functions, the city - and/or regional - transportation system, and land use as something that forms the preconditions for what we both need to and can do within curbside management.

The framework consists of five functions:

- Public space and services
- Access for people
- Storage for vehicles
- Access for goods
- Retail activities

The main tools that are in play are:

- Space allocation
- Design
- Time restrictions
- Pricing

The framework also proposes a set of indicators for working with these functions.

The important notion in this report is that curbside management is about the move away from long-time storage dedicated to private vehicles to the allocation of this space to other functions. The focus of this report is the transportation related to the functions mentioned above.

Overview of literature on Dynamic Curbside Management

The field of dynamic curbside management, covering its functions and tools, rests on different research categories. To identify barriers to implementing dynamic curbside management as well as ways to overcome them, we need to get a better understanding of the current knowledge on the different research categories. Starting from the ITF study (2018) and the functions defined above, the main categories that have been identified in relation to curb access demand are:

- On-street parking management
- Transportation Network Companies (TNCs)
- Autonomous Vehicles
- On-street freight management
- Space allocation, shifting from storage for vehicles to other functions
- Enforcement
- Data collection methods

In this chapter we briefly describe the identified categories to give an insight into the main questions within each category and how this relates to dynamic curbside management.

On-street parking management

To be able to move away from the long-term storage of cars, there is a common agreement on the need to achieve more efficient parking management. Effective on-street parking management is as much an ingredient in curbside management as an enabler to introduce other functions. Contested curb sections may still include parking but it needs to shift to:

- Pricing parking at the right level
- Focusing on availability

There is a vast literature on the benefits and potentials with pricing parking with a demand-responsive approach, mostly stemming from prominent scholars like Donald Shoup (1997). The most common benefits being mentioned are reduced search traffic, higher parking revenues, increase in local economic activity. The ideas of Shoup are the foundation for both handbooks like Barter's *On-Street Parking Management An International Toolkit* (2016), the reports mentioned above from NACTO (2017), ITF (2018), and ITE (2018), and for a vast amount of studies using different traffic model approaches (more on this below).

A big part of the literature on on-street parking management consists of traffic modelling studies which tries to find an optimum for either pricing, restrictions or space allocation with the objective to mitigate different negative effects. Methods such as equilibrium models (van Nieuwkoop, Renger H.; Axhausen, Kay W.; Rutherford, 2016) and dynamic models (Jakob et al., 2020) shows that traffic performance can be increased with improved pricing policies for parking at the curb. Restrictions at the curbside (such as no allowed stopping or reduced availability) may also give other complications on the traffic beside cruising for an available slot. One common consequence in many cities is double parking or illegal stopping. The potential negative effect from double parking on traffic flow and congestion has been modelled by for example Gao & Ozbay (2016) and Simoni & Claudel (2018).

The idea of pricing as a tool for parking management is important for curbside management since it establishes (1) the acceptance for pricing the curb as a measure balancing demand and availability, (2) the focus on availability (which is essential for the access-oriented functions) as a performance indicator, and (3) a holistic area-wide parking management approach (including off-street parking).

Even though the theoretical starting points for using pricing are the same, the policy development around on-street parking management is much more established than for curbside management. A study on larger U.S municipalities shows that curbside management is starting to be formally included as a topic of its own, however mostly together with on-street parking management (Butrina et al., 2020).

Transportation Network Companies, On-street freight management and Autonomous Vehicles

Each of these three categories – transportation network companies, on street freight management and autonomous vehicles - of course have their respective needs and characteristics. They are grouped here since they together are the main drivers for the picture of the curb as a contested place, today and in a potential future. Cities with an increase in TNCs and deliveries have experienced a growing need to manage problems like illegal stopping and double parking, and to mitigate negative effects on traffic flow and traffic safety. On a more strategic level, cities must of course explore their options to make sure that their curb management of these categories are aligned with their broader goals. How cities work with curb space allocation is described in the next chapter below.

Transportation Network Companies

The question whether TNCs decrease or increase congestion on city streets has had conflicting answers. Erhardt et al. (2019) showed that TNCs were the biggest contributor to the growth in congestion in San Francisco between 2010 and 2016. As demand for curbspace with the growth of TNCs has increased (Butrina et al., 2020), studies on the other hand suggest that TNCs potentially have lowered the demand for parking, see for example Henao & Marshall (2019). The measures introduced at the curb do to some extent both affect demand for curb space and individual mode choices. Henao & Marshall (2019) also showed that the “cost” of parking (for example price, time restrictions and search time) is a reason for using TNCs instead of using a private car.

On-street freight management

The growth in demand for deliveries as well as the shift in space allocation from parking to other functions have increased the competition for curb access for freight activities. One problem in many cities is that on-street freight management typically has focused on loading for commercial demands and not on the growing deliveries of goods to consumers. (Chen et al., 2017)

Understanding the needs and the dynamics of the freight sector is critical in managing deliveries at the curb. Many cities have implemented urban freight measures aimed at for example either lowering demand at the curb (Campbell et al., 2018), directing loading activities to off-peak hours (Dey et al., 2019) or introducing smarter, safer and less-polluting last-mile solutions (Barone & Roach, 2016). Such measures are of course of great interest since they, to a great extent, set the preconditions for curbside management – plus, they also highlight that the solutions for a better curb situation for deliveries often are found somewhere other than the curb.

As for parking management, this field has a vast literature with different simulations and modelling of measures both off- and on-street. Simoni & Claudel (2018) have looked into urban freight movements and evaluated the problem with double-parking from a city logistics perspective and found shifting to off-peak deliveries to be an efficient measure. The potential with off-peak deliveries is amplified by Campbell et al. (2018) who have assessed the needs of freight and service related on-street commercial activities using a demand management model. Their findings also include the importance of trying to minimise loading duration, which has a close correlation with walking time from loading space to destination.

The importance of short walking distances was outlined in a study on Lisbon in 2014 which found the optimal maximum walking distance to be around 50 meters. (Alho & de Abreu e Silva, 2014)

Autonomous Vehicles

To what extent a city must prepare for autonomous vehicles is a question that lies outside of the scope of this report. Much of the literature on autonomous vehicles that is relevant for curbside management relies on the assumption that fully automated vehicles will be developed in a near future. Based on that assumption there are strategies to harness the potential benefits that comes with the impact of the new technology (Diehl, 2018), evaluation of the effects on the need for parking (Zhang & Guhathakurta, 2017), the call for cities to prepare for autonomous vehicles (Clark, 2019; Riggs, 2019), and much more.

Others argue that the problems with autonomous vehicles functioning in an uncontrolled domain like a city with the presence, and often prioritisation, of pedestrians and cyclists, makes it hard to predict the large-scale deployment of fully autonomous vehicles in cities in a near future. A recent report on the impacts of autonomous vehicles and their implications for transportation planning predicts that the effects on the curb might not be significant before the 2050s or 2060s (Litman, 2020).

Space allocation

The allocation of space (and time) at the curb to different functions and users is the main theme in all the categories above. To be able to understand it regardless to the specific functions mentioned above, this section is dedicated to this topic on its own.

The starting point for the literature on allocating space at the curb is the shift away from storage for vehicles to other functions. The strategies mentioned above from cities like Seattle and San Francisco are examples of a contemporary trend in policy documents to consider city streets as multifunctional places rather than solely dedicated to vehicle mobility and storage. This evolution within transport policy perspectives to functionally group streets into different classes based on their purpose and characteristics, including streets as places, has, by among others, been described in a recent report from the Horizon 2020 project MORE (TUD & UCL, 2019).

The need for space at the curb is likely the reason why actors like TNCs have sponsored reports to improve curb space productivity, including promoting a metric called the “Curb Productivity Index”. The metric could be used to calculate the level of activity at the curb within a specific time frame (Fehr & Peers, 2018). A more detailed approach with a cost-benefit analysis process has been developed by Potter & Weinberger (2020). Their paper suggests a tool for quantifying benefits to compare different functions in the allocation of curb space.

The fact that commercial users more often are claiming curb space could potentially be a risk for an equitable distribution of street space. In an evolving urban realm and in a situation where the curb

management is highly inefficient, cities might feel inclined to answer to such claims. Commercial entities have a strong interest and see a great potential in influencing cities to accommodate their needs at the curb. Other users often don't have the same resources or platforms to voice their needs. Marsden et al. (2020) therefore argue that governments “*need to develop a clear multi-use and multi-user framework for thinking about streets which ensures that regulatory recodification is properly thought through and allocates rights to maximise wider public goals*”. Without it, there is a clear risk of privatisation of a public good.

Enforcement

A great challenge with the increase in TNCs and deliveries is that enforcing short stops is difficult, due the short time frame of the activity, without large investments in technology or human resources (Pérez, Benito O.; Kerwin, Joseph; Lipscomb, David; Meggs, 2020). And even with the introduction of new technology there are still challenges with enforcement that need to be solved.

Marsden et al. (2020) points to a set of challenges for enforcing the rules at the curb. The challenges appear when cities aiming at greater curb efficiency move forward with closing the gap between the informal practices in the street and the expressed rules. If one wants to manage the curb smarter relying on technology and computational systems, it's necessary to define more clearly what is allowed and where. Traffic management regulations and orders must be correctly expressed with a balance between supply and demand which correlates with both user needs and public acceptance. Today, cities often don't have enough information on different uses and users which potentially could undermine the legitimacy of the rules that are to be enforced. When introducing the use of technology in enforcement this raises significant concerns about privacy and secure data management.

Efficient enforcement also stresses the need for standardisation in both traffic management regulations, data management and communication protocols. Marsden et al. (Marsden et al., 2020) notes that many of the initiatives around this tend to be driven from a private perspective. The concern and awareness of governments and the EU are however growing. National and international initiatives are being developed on various levels.

Data collection methods

Systematic data collection about usage and local needs is critical for (1) managing the existing functions at the curb more efficiently, (2) for facilitating the introduction of other functions, and (3) for enabling a future dynamic management approach.

To understand the actual demand and efficiency, cities need to collect information on occupancy and availability. As summarized in Dey et al. (2017), the available detection methods include in-ground sensors, manual data collection, payment data, crowdsourcing applications, various cameras (mounted or portable) and license plate recognition (often also referred to as automatic number plate recognition).

While manual data collection does not require investment in technology, it will require more labour costs than other methods (Dey et al., 2017). The expensive data collection will only motivate spot checks which does not yield real time data. In a pilot study conducted in Washington D.C., manual data collection was considered inadequate to serve the districts future curbside management needs, which included being able to introduce demand-responsive pricing at the curb for both parking, loading and stopping activities.

Usage of in-ground sensors provided real-time data but were costly (Dey et al., 2017). In the pilot study in Washington D.C., the municipality experienced various issues with the technique including battery life and occasional network failures. When using in-ground sensors, District of Columbia discovered that it was enough to only collect a part of the data: a 50 % coverage of parking spaces gave close to the same accuracy of what could be collected by a 100 % coverage.

Using payment data solely to predict the occupancy would be misleading because of vehicles parking without paying (Dey et al., 2017). In the pilot study in District of Columbia, the payment rate varied between 31 to 98 %. The payment data are therefore considered unable to alone eliminate the need of other data for occupancy information.

In San Francisco, the municipality took an approach to provide real-time information using payment data, by creating a linear model that was estimated using real-life data from in-ground sensors used during the SFpark pilot. The data was captured over a 2.5-year period and included occupancy and payment rate as well as day of week and neighbourhood type. The model has made it possible to perform demand-responsive rate adjustments without the use of actual real-time occupancy data (SFMTA, 2014).

Cameras can have very different performances depending on how they are used: If they are mounted, if they must be moved around or if they are attached to a vehicle. Also, the way the data is collected can affect the performance: if they are analysed using computer vision algorithms or if they are reviewed manually.

Dey et al. (2016) concludes that one of the first obstacles to take on is the problem with not having demarcated individual parking spaces. This situation can lead to a discrepancy between the theoretical number of available parking spaces and the actual capacity when vehicles park closer to or further away from each other. Overall a pay-by-space scheme has shown to be more efficient when occupancy is high. Also, if the detection is made with in-ground sensors, non-demarcated parking spaces will require a larger number of sensors. Because of this, New York City found that cameras were more applicable when capturing occupancy data on spaces that weren't demarcated (Kazis, 2012).

In summary, there is not one piece of technology that will fit every situation or alone can provide sufficient data. Instead, cities have to rely on a several different technologies and data sources depending on local characteristics and preconditions (Dey et al., 2017). The growth in smartphone applications for managing the curbside promise the potential of using crowdsourced data. This data stream could be part of a future comprehensive mobility data approach (Davis 2019).

Identified barriers

Governance and Financing

- **Silo-organisations** – the responsibilities for the managing the functions at the curb are usually divided among different agencies

In Dey et al. (2017), it was identified that a split up in responsibility between different municipal agencies led to difficulties in coordination. As an example, the parking policy and the parking enforcement in Washington DC is handled by two separate agencies, while the police department is responsible for some additional enforcement.

- **Staffing – resources** – municipalities lacking capabilities

Poor staffing and resources can be a limiting factor when trying to implement smarter operation. An example is when municipalities don't have the resources to process or make new data streams accessible for managing the use of the curb. (Butrina et al., 2020) With a growing market of sensors and solutions for assisting with curb management, it's likely that unit and service prices will go down with time and competition. At the same time, it could be a barrier for cities with limited resources to know what technology to invest in and when.

- **Shifting revenue streams** – losing income from for example parking fees

When moving away from storage for vehicles, municipalities often lose a direct, secure and tangible revenue stream. The new function or functions replacing the parking spaces often mean a more indirect or insecure revenue stream, which might also be harder to estimate. As the San Francisco MTA, municipalities might want to look for other options for pricing curb use and by doing so creating new revenue sources. (SFMTA, 2020)

- **Legislation** – the need for flexible regulations and legal backing

For truly dynamic curbside management, there is a need for regulations allowing different user groups to use the curb at the same time. Even a sequential allocation to different functions could sometimes be a challenge. (Marsden et al., 2020) There is also the already mentioned discrepancies between how regulations are expressed in the street, what really is regulated, and the practice in the street.

Another barrier regarding legislation is that municipalities sometimes don't have the possibility to implement measures or tools since they don't have the necessary legal backing from higher levels of government. (Barter, 2016)

- **Safe and secure data protection and systems**

New data sources which collect so called "passive data", for example through cell phones and vehicles, and new technologies, for data processing and analysing, pose a great potential for better designed measures at the curb. With introducing new technology to manage demand at the curb and for collecting data governments at different levels, it is important to set up data repositories that are able to both securely hold mobility data and to provide just the right level of access for public planning agencies and researchers. (D'Agostino et al., 2019)

Where applications are controlling different facilities and systems in a city these must of course also be safe and secure and be able to withstand disruptions and attacks.

User needs and public acceptance

- **The need to be user friendly**

Where the goal is a curb that potentially has different functions depending on both time and demand, there are evident barriers to address where users must (1) be able to understand a measure before stopping at the curb (for example is there a charge for stopping, and if so, how much?), and (2) be able to understand any user interfaces that are introduced (for example a smartphone application for booking in advance and/or payment).

There is already today a challenge to communicate on the rules at the curb and to design application user interfaces, especially so in cities with a language diversity and sometimes even illiteracy. With the introduction of dynamic management with flexible rules expressed with signages and markings, this becomes a barrier for cities to address. After all, the number of violations at the curb is most likely an indicator of an ill-designed solution and should be used as a feedback loop to change it.

- **Equity issues**

Sometimes a measure could be implemented without taking user needs into account. For example, a city could opt for abandoning all parking payment options in a street except for phone payment. This would, however, exclude or make it much harder for certain groups, often vulnerable or marginalised, to use the parking spaces, which wouldn't be a desired scenario.

- **Personal data protection**

Safe and secure data protections systems are critical to protect the privacy of users and their interactions with the curb. The privacy of every individual must be guaranteed in every application and solution that a city chose to implement. If not, this might undermine an otherwise well-designed measure.

- **Knowledge gap**

The literature overview shows that there is only a limited number of physical trials and pilots for different functions within the curbside management framework. Most of the evaluation of these are in the form of self-assessments and self-evaluations, for example by the company who also provided the solution that was trialled. When cities have evaluated the effectiveness of their own pilots, they often lack the perspectives and needs of the end user.

- **Shifting status quo**

Whenever a change is brought into the urban landscape an outcry from concerned stakeholders is to be expected. As shown in multiple cases, for example by Börjesson et al. (2016) regarding congestion pricing, the status quo bias as an explanation for the resistance against a new measure or policy “*seems to be a general phenomenon: the change is resisted partly just because it is a change*”.

- **Privatisation**

As shown above, the allocation of curb space in contested locations could, to some extent, be at risk of being exclusively granted to private companies like TNCs or freight operators. Cities who have implemented so called Pick-up and drop-off zones in downtown locations (abbreviated PUDOs) (Schaller, 2019) have done so by for example restricting access to users of a specific application (Pérez, Benito O.; Kerwin, Joseph; Lipscomb, David; Meggs, 2020). While the benefits of a more structured and efficient situation at the curb are evident, there must always be the discussion about the disadvantages for other users.

- **Public consultation and dissemination**

In a pilot study conducted by Dey et al. (2017), it was identified that an ill-timed temporal closure of on-street parking (for the installation of equipment for occupancy) could create a negative perception of a curbside management measure at an early stage. This could damage the public acceptance to the project at a later stage.

Another pilot study conducted in District of Columbia aimed to introduce demand-driven hourly parking meter rates. In the study area, the municipality introduced in-street sensors on the on-street parking places to enable real-time detection. The occupancy was studied for a period of a year. It was discovered that the variation in occupancy from day to day was strongly dependent on irregular occurrences of events at a local arena. The project team did, however, not find it motivated to discriminate between event days and non-event days in the pricing strategy, because of the apprehension that it would be difficult to reach public acceptance for such a measure.

In the D.C. pilot study evaluation, it was concluded that communication between agencies and to the public was important in reaching public acceptance and foreseeing potential issues.

Mobility concepts

New mobility concepts and services are often part of the functions that are to be managed at the curb, or part of the tools and technology that they rely on for being implemented. Hence, there are no direct barrier for implementing dynamic curbside management regarding this transition area. Indirectly, since a more efficient curbside management often include the prioritisation of and space allocation to new services, there is always the risk of a city promoting immature business models at the curb which later prompts the city to roll-back the change.

System design/technology

- **Existing and new systems**

Cities often have existing systems for managing different functions which have been procured for a longer period. New ways of working may either require them to be integrated with new solutions and technology or may require them to communicate with each other in an efficient way. This is maybe not a barrier with a longer time frame but rather something that could potentially delay an implementation of a measure for a few years.

- **Coding the curb**

Many of the solutions for a more sophisticated curbside management relies on the assumption, that cities have an accessible digital spatial inventory of everything that happens at the curb and all regulations that are in place. This is unfortunately often not the case.

- **Enforcement**

The nature of TNCs and deliveries of consumer goods means short time for stopping and dwelling, which is hard to enforce. While new technology and solutions have the potential to solve some of the problems with enforcement, the biggest problem seem to be how to guarantee compliance in a curb pricing scheme without incentivising unsafe behaviour. San Francisco MTA (2020) points to the risk with pricing loading bays which potentially could lead to more double-parking or stopping in the adjacent traffic lane. Camera-based systems alone are at this point in time not advanced enough to identify all activities that need to be enforced. Plus, the use of cameras is a serious privacy concern, which in many countries leads to cameras either being heavily restricted or even prohibited in public areas.

- **Lack of standards**

For unlocking many of the benefits with more efficient curbside management and new mobility services, there is a need for standardising. For example, this need covers the question of how the functions at the curb are coded, how data is structured, and how operating devices and vehicles can communicate with the curb. Even though there are several initiatives underway, there are today several question marks regarding how a city should design their systems. After all, cities can't themselves afford to develop their own standards for every aspect involved.

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